

PubMed search strategy

Search terms

#1 general practitioner*[Title/Abstract] OR primary healthcare[Title/Abstract] OR primary health care[Title/Abstract] OR primary medical care[Title/Abstract] OR general practice*[Title/Abstract] OR family physician*[Title/Abstract] OR family doctor*[Title/Abstract] OR family practitioner*[Title/Abstract] OR "primary care physician"[Title/Abstract] OR "primary health care"[MeSH]

#2 recruit*[Title/Abstract]

#3 trial*[Title/Abstract] OR "Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh]

#4 #1 AND #2 AND #3

#5 Limit to English

#6 Limit to Humans